

Conversion Therapy, Suicidality, and Running Away: An Analysis of Transgender Youth in the U.S.*

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Abstract

This study provides evidence of the deleterious effects of conversion therapy on the mental health and wellbeing of transgender youth in the U.S. We create a retrospective panel of transgender youth using the 2015 U.S. Transgender Survey to test how exposure to conversion therapy affects the likelihood of attempting suicide and running away from home. The empirical approach employs a stacked difference-in-differences design. Results indicate that exposure to conversion therapy substantially increases the likelihood a transgender adolescent will attempt suicide and run away. The average treatment effect on treated (ATT) of conversion therapy on having attempted suicide is an increase of 17 percentage points, which amounts to a 55% increase in the risk of attempting suicide, and the ATT on the risk of running away is an increase of 7.8 percentage points, which amount to a more than doubling in the risk of running away. These effects are largest when exposure to conversion therapy occurs at a young age (11-14).

Keywords: Transgender, Conversion Therapy, Mental Health, Suicide

JEL Codes: I14, I18, I31, J15

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I. Introduction

Transgender individuals in the U.S. still face widespread stigma, discrimination, and violence (Winter et al., 2016; Carpenter et al., 2020). Problems of stigma and discrimination can lead to poor physical and mental health outcomes, and gender minority stress and gender dysphoria lie at the root of these inequities (Meyer, 2003; Turban et al., 2022). Hence any changes that help to mitigate these root causes, including improved access to health insurance and health care services – especially gender-affirming care – will help to close the health gaps (Mann et al., 2022; Campbell and Rodgers, 2022). A primary target is the lack of family acceptance and support, which directly contributes to stress and dysphoria and also acts as a block against access to insurance and health care. In fact, Kundu et al. (2022) find that being insulted by one’s parents or an adult during childhood ranks among the top three correlates of suicidal thoughts in the past year among a sample of sexual and gender minority young adults in Canada. Hostile parents, in turn, often encourage or coerce their transgender children into undergoing sexual orientation or gender identity change efforts, often referred to as conversion therapy. This type of therapy, usually provided by counselors or religious advisors, aims to change an individual’s sexual orientation or to discourage individuals, especially adolescents, from identifying as transgender or from expressing themselves in gender-diverse ways.

Most professional associations related to mental health and the health of young people have critiqued conversion therapy as being ineffective at best and harmful at worst, and 20 states have banned the practice (Mallory et al., 2019; Movement Advancement Project, 2022). However, there is very little quantitative evidence on the effects of conversion therapy on measures of mental health and wellbeing among trans and gender-diverse youth. Although quite a few studies across disciplines have been published on conversion therapy (e.g. James et al., 2016; Turban et al., 2020; Higbee et al., 2022), to our knowledge, none of them address important sources of selection into conversion therapy as explained below.

Our goal is to fill this gap by using data from the 2015 U.S. Transgender Survey (USTS) to examine the effect of conversion therapy on the risk of attempting suicide and running away for transgender adolescents. Since unobservable characteristics such as socioeconomic status and upbringing may affect both conversion therapy exposure and measures of wellbeing, simple correlations that do not account for differences in characteristics between the treated and control groups prior to conversion therapy exposure may be misleading, and they cannot prove that young people who are subjected to conversion therapy are at a greater risk of poor wellbeing because of the therapy. For example, trans youth exposed to conversion therapy may have had other disadvantages (such as living in a hostile community or having lower socioeconomic status) that could explain both the conversion therapy participation and

the poor wellbeing, or they may have had poor wellbeing that led their parents to consider conversion therapy. To identify the effect of conversion therapy on measures of wellbeing, we utilize a difference-in-differences (DID) approach. This approach allows us to estimate a substantive treatment effect of conversion therapy on the risk of attempting suicide and running away for transgender adolescents.

By comparing transgender adolescents who are exposed to conversion therapy (treated group) with those who are either never exposed or are exposed later on (control group), we find that conversion therapy increases the risk of attempting suicide by 17 percentage points, which amounts to a 55% increase in the risk of attempting suicide, and running away by 7.8 percentage points, more than doubling the risk of running away. The effects are largest when exposure to conversion therapy occurs at a young age (11-14). These estimates are compelling not only because they pass a battery of falsification and robustness tests, but also because the rate of attempting suicide and running away is remarkably similar in both level and trend between the treated and control groups over the five years preceding conversion therapy. Furthermore and most importantly, the estimates hold when we exploit only the precise timing of conversion therapy, limiting the control group to those who are exposed to conversion therapy one year after the treated group.

Our paper contributes to the literature on transgender well-being. Numerous studies have shown that transgender individuals are more likely to report poor general, physical, and mental health compared to their cisgender counterparts (Meyer et al., 2017; Cicero et al., 2020). Mental health disparities are particularly stark, with considerably higher rates of depression, anxiety, PTSD, suicidality, and substance abuse in the U.S. transgender community (Haas et al., 2014; Marshall et al., 2016; Reisner et al., 2016; Downing and Przedworski, 2018; Lagos, 2018). Data from the USTS indicate that 40% of respondents had attempted suicide at least once in their lifetime, a rate that exceeds that of the general population by a factor of close to nine (James et al., 2016). Moreover, in a 2017 survey of U.S. high school students, 34.6% of the transgender students had attempted suicide compared to 5.5% of cisgender male students and 9.1% of cisgender female students (Johns et al., 2019). These kinds of mental health disparities also have repercussions for the labor market, with losses in human capital and labor productivity (e.g. Lerner and Henke, 2008; Chatterji et al., 2011; Rivera et al., 2017; Dow et al., 2020).

For both indicators we examine, risk factors include depression, lack of family and community support, and victimization (Thompson and Pillai, 2006). Although the magnitude of welfare losses seems at least an order of magnitude larger for suicide attempts compared to running away, we argue that running away is an important indicator of wellbeing because this action increases the subsequent risk of drug addiction, homelessness, sexual risk taking,

dropping out of school, criminal activity, and additional depressive symptoms (Kaufman and Widom, 1999; Tucker et al., 2011; Rice et al., 2013; Aratani and Cooper, 2015).

This study also offers timely evidence to inform the discussion of public policies relating to transgender health. A number of states, especially those with Republican-led governments, have institutionalized bias against transgender individuals with, for example, laws that prohibit transgender girls from participating in girls' sports, provisions that exclude gender-affirming care from Medicaid coverage, and even outright bans on the provision of gender-affirming care. On the other hand, several states have recently introduced gender affirming policies, such as conversion therapy bans that prohibit the practice of gender identity change efforts, as well as gender marker laws that allow people to change their gender on official documents such as birth certificates and drivers licenses (Mann, 2021). Such efforts that promote more inclusion contribute to improved wellbeing (White Hughto et al., 2015). For example, having fully gender-concordant identity documents is associated with a 32% decrease in severe psychological distress and up to a 25% reduction in suicide risk (Scheim et al., 2020). These policy changes have placed transgender issues in the national media spotlight and increased the need for empirical evidence on the possible welfare effects of transgender-related policies and practices. However, little is known about the effect of either affirming or exclusionary laws, given a relative dearth of data that allow the identification of transgender individuals. By using the U.S. Transgender Survey – the largest survey of transgender individuals of its kind – and recently-developed estimation techniques, this study aims to contribute new evidence on welfare outcomes associated with conversion therapy that should help to inform policy discussions of these kinds of laws.

II. Background: Conversion Therapy

The underlying premise of conversion therapy – sometimes referred to as reparative therapy – is that lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, and queer (LGBTQ) individuals have a mental illness that needs to be cured, and the underlying objective is to change the sexual orientation or gender identity of that person. Efforts by health care practitioners and religious advisors to use conversion therapy to change someone's sexual orientation or gender identity date back to the 1890s and include a variety of techniques (Mallory et al., 2019). The most common technique now is talk therapy, but earlier forms of therapy based on pseudoscience included “aversive” techniques that entailed subjecting the individual to electrical shocks, nausea-inducing substances, paralysis, prompts to inflict self-harm, covert sensitization, and orgasmic reconditioning (Glassgold et al., 2009). Non-aversive techniques such as hypnosis

and affection training were also used in an attempt to change thoughts and behaviors around sexuality and gender identity ([Glassgold et al., 2009](#)).

There is no credible peer-reviewed evidence showing that conversion therapy can actually change a person's sexual orientation or gender therapy. In the case of sexual orientation, a systematic review of peer-reviewed articles about conversion therapy found 13 studies containing primary research. Twelve of those studies found that conversion therapy for sexual orientation was either ineffective or harmful, and the 13th study had enough problematic research design issues to render the claimed results implausible ([What We Know Project, 2016](#)). This conclusion about the ineffectiveness of conversion therapy in achieving its intended purpose builds on earlier scholarship about the dubious ethics of conversion therapy as well as the potential for contributing to adverse outcomes such as anxiety and depression, suicidality, and social isolation ([Haldeman, 1994](#); [Byne et al., 2012](#); [Coleman et al., 2012](#); [Wallace and Russell, 2013](#)). In the case of gender identity, there are no peer-reviewed studies proving the efficacy of conversion therapy in achieving its intended goal, while two studies have shown a correlation between exposure to conversion therapy and adverse mental health indicators for transgender individuals ([James et al., 2016](#); [Turban et al., 2020](#)).

The American Psychological Association, the Endocrine Society, the American Academy of Pediatrics, the Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Association, and the American Psychiatric Association have all formally endorsed gender-affirming care as the only acceptable approach to therapeutic care for transgender individuals ([Bazelon, 2022](#)). They oppose all legislative efforts to prevent transgender and gender non-binary youth from accessing these services. These organizations have also discredited conversion therapy. For example, in its 2018 policy statement on care for transgender and gender-diverse youth, the American Academy of Pediatrics wrote that conversion therapy is not only unsuccessful but also inappropriate, deleterious, unfair, and deceptive ([Rafferty et al., 2018](#)). Moreover, the Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Association conducted a careful review of clinical guidelines and professional association reports and concluded that conversion therapy is “coercive, can be harmful, and should not be part of behavioral health treatment,” ([SAMHSA, 2015](#)).

Because advocates have deemed conversion therapy practices as harmful for LGBTQ minors, numerous states have passed legislation that prohibits licensed mental health professionals from subjecting LGBTQ minors to such practices. To date, 20 states plus the District of Columbia have complete bans on conversion therapy for minors ([Movement Advancement Project, 2022](#)). However, these bans are fairly recent, and religious providers are not covered by the bans. California was the first state to ban conversion therapy in 2012, followed by New Jersey and the District of Columbia within the next two years; most other states that do ban conversion therapy did not do so until 2017 and beyond. Another eight states have

partial bans or legislation tied up in court, and 22 states have no laws on conversion therapy ([Movement Advancement Project, 2022](#)).

These bans are important for a number of reasons, not least because transgender individuals make up a non-negligible part of the U.S. population. Among all individuals ages 13 and above, approximately 0.6% are transgender, which amounts to 1.6 million people ([Herman et al., 2022](#)). On average, the transgender population is younger than the overall U.S. population: of those individuals who identify as transgender, 18% are youths ages 13-17, while this age group constitutes less than 8% of the total U.S. population. These numbers have risen since 2017, the last time such estimates were generated, reflecting an increase in social acceptance among young people in being transgender, gender diverse, or non-binary ([Herman et al., 2022](#)).

Going to conversion therapy can influence mental health and wellbeing outcomes directly through the prolonging and intensification of gender dysphoria and gender minority stress since it is by construct a homophobic/transphobic institution in a hostile environment. It can also affect mental health and wellbeing indirectly through the denial of gender-affirming care. By implication, a transgender young person who has been placed into conversion therapy most likely is not receiving gender-affirming care, the latter being associated with improved health outcomes. A number of studies have found an association between access to gender-affirming care and improved health outcomes, including a lower incidence of suicide ideation and suicide attempts (e.g. [Turban et al., 2022](#); [Green et al., 2022](#)). [Mann et al. \(2022\)](#) take this research one step further and find a positive effect of Medicaid coverage for gender-affirming care on measures of mental health for transgender beneficiaries.

Scholars and practitioners generally agree that support from family members is critical for preventing LGBTQ youth from experiencing negative outcomes, and especially the worst possible outcomes such as suicide attempts and running away from home ([Ryan et al., 2009, 2010](#); [Kosciw et al., 2020](#)). Ridiculing a child, refusing to use their preferred name and pronoun, and preventing them from interacting with LGBTQ friends are forms of family rejection and trauma associated with poor mental health outcomes for LGBTQ youth. Requests for conversion therapy almost always come from parents and guardians rather than the trans youth themselves, making conversion therapy another form of family rejection ([Glassgold et al., 2009](#)). Adolescents do not have the legal authority to make their own medical decisions, so they often have no choice but to abide by their parents' demands to attend conversion therapy ([Byne, 2016](#)). The [Family Acceptance Project \(2022\)](#) notes that sending LGBTQ children to mental health professionals and religious leaders to change their identity is usually perceived as “the most risk-inducing behavior that parents can engage in.” Demonstrating an adverse effect of conversion therapy would thus add to scholarship on the health and

wellbeing of trans and gender-diverse youth.

III. Data Description and Methodology

III.A. United States Transgender Survey

Our analysis utilizes the 2015 wave of the **U.S. Transgender Survey**. The USTS – the largest survey of transgender people ever collected – has 27,715 respondents from all fifty states plus the District of Columbia, U.S. territories, and U.S. military bases abroad. The National Center for Transgender Equality conducted this survey of transgender adults (18 and older) in the summer of 2015 as a follow-up to their inaugural 2008-09 National Transgender Discrimination Survey (NTDS). It documents the lives and experiences of trans individuals, with detailed information on a range of indicators, including education, employment, race, family life, health status, marital status, and access to healthcare. As such, the USTS and NTDS have been used extensively to analyze the outcomes of transgender individuals (e.g. Bakko and Kattari, 2020; Budge et al., 2016; Goldenberg et al., 2020).

We used two measures of mental health and wellbeing from the USTS for the empirical analysis: suicide attempts and running away. In the USTS, suicide attempts and running away are both self-reported, and for each outcome we code respondents who do not know the answer or refuse to respond as missing. For suicide attempts, respondents are asked “At any time in your life, did you try to kill yourself?” If the answer is yes, respondents are also asked about the number of attempts as well as the age when the first attempt was made. For running away from home, respondents are asked “Did you ever run away from home because you are trans?” If the answer is yes, respondents are also asked the age when they ran away. For the key independent variable to measure exposure to conversion therapy, respondents are asked “Did any professional (such as a psychologist, counselor, religious advisor) try to make you identify only with your sex assigned at birth (in other words, try to stop you being trans)?” If the answer is yes, respondents are also asked the age at which this first happened.

Our estimations include four indicators for social transitioning: ever feeling one’s gender was different, ever thinking of oneself as transgender, ever telling another that they are transgender, and ever living full-time as the gender of their gender identity. The following survey questions are used to measure these indicators: (1) “At about what age did you begin to feel that your gender was “different” from your assigned birth sex?” (2) “At about what age did you start to think you were trans (even if you did not know the word for it)?” (3) “At about what age did you first start to tell others that you were trans (even if you did not use that word)?” (4) “How old were you when you started to live full-time in a gender

that is different from the one assigned to you at birth?” Because we know the ages when the respondents first experienced these events, we are able to construct cohort-specific variables for these social transitioning indicators by coding them as equal to one if the respondent first experienced each event by a particular year, and zero otherwise.

The USTS is an online survey that allows respondents to self-identify as transgender, so the survey includes people at various stages of transition, and it allows for a broad interpretation of trans – including transgender, trans, genderqueer, and non-binary identities (Shannon, 2022). Although it is not a random sample, the USTS does contain vital information on mental health, wellbeing, and experience with conversion therapy that is not available elsewhere, including the Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System (BRFSS). While the BRFSS does include information about gender identity as well as self-reported health status, it does not have questions on conversion therapy, suicide attempts, or running away. A comparison of key demographic indicators in the USTS with the sample of transgender adults in the BRFSS indicates that the USTS sample is younger, more white, more educated, more likely to report good health, and more likely to have a job and an income that exceeds \$50,000 (Shannon, 2022). These demographic differences indicate that treatment effect estimates using the USTS, even if internally valid, may not reflect the overall transgender population if the treatment effects are heterogeneous. We do not find evidence of heterogeneity by pre-exposure demographics (the estimates are notably precise), providing some assurance.

III.B. Data Limitations

The USTS was not collected with a randomized sampling strategy, and it was only distributed online. To correct for discrepancies in the demographic composition of its sample, and to offset possible internet survey bias and other potential problems with survey access, the USTS team engaged in extensive outreach efforts to recruit respondents. These efforts included working with a network of advocacy groups and organizations to share information about the survey, holding survey-taking events, and offering cash-prize incentives (James et al., 2016). These efforts could also help to mitigate some of the possible undercounting of homeless transgender individuals, which matters for our study since we examine running away from home, a predictor of homelessness. This point is supported with data from the National Longitudinal Survey of Youth (NLSY), which is also subject to the same data limitation. Brakenhoff et al. (2015) find that 18% of NLSY respondents had run away from home before turning 17; 40% of those individuals had done so at least twice, and multiple runaway experiences more than doubled the odds of homelessness compared to those who never ran away.

Another limitation of the survey is that the question we use to measure exposure to

conversion therapy does not explicitly use the term “conversion” or “therapy”, which could reflect efforts by the USTS team to use accessible language based on lived experiences (ICPSR, 2015). A strength of the wording of this question is that it specifically asks whether a professional tried to stop the respondent from being trans, which helps to weed out other kinds of conversion efforts attempted by non-professional practitioners (Maccio, 2010). However, a potential limitation of the wording is that it is broad enough to encompass counseling and techniques that may not be labeled as conversion therapy but still have the same intent. For example, someone who experienced a school counselor trying to police gender could answer yes to this question even though that respondent did not receive therapy per se.

Evidence from the [Trevor Project \(2019\)](#) indicates that this wording matters: in their survey of LGBTQ youth, two-thirds of respondents had experienced “someone” attempting to convince them to change their sexual orientation or gender identity, while this share dropped to 5% when the wording of the question was changed to specifically ask if they had experienced conversion therapy. In comparison, 13% of the USTS sample answered yes to the conversion therapy question, which suggests that the USTS question is reasonably close to capturing experiences with conversion therapy, even though it does not identify whether a therapeutic service was provided or what kind of a professional provided the conversion therapy. To help give further validity to using this question in the USTS, we examine the share of USTS respondents who report exposure to conversion therapy across regions. As shown in Online Appendix Figure [A.1](#), which shows the share of respondents who had conversion therapy at some point in their lives by state of birth, conversion therapy is relatively common in the south and in rural western states such as Utah and Idaho. Conversion therapy is relatively uncommon in democratic-leaning areas such as the western coast and the northeastern US. These results are fairly intuitive and lend support to our assertion that this question yields a valid measure of exposure to conversion therapy.

There are three additional sampling issues. First, we cannot observe people for whom conversion therapy was successful. This should not be a problem for our estimates given the known low efficacy of conversion therapy in the case of sexual orientation ([What We Know Project, 2016](#)). Second, we cannot observe people who actually died by suicide. If conversion therapy increases the incidence and lethality of suicide attempts, then people who were most adversely affected by conversion therapy will die, selecting out of the sample. This selection on mortality would then disproportionately decrease the share of respondents who both had conversion therapy and attempted suicide afterwards, attenuating the estimates. The selection on mortality may be more severe for older cohorts, given the higher likelihood of prior attempts during adolescence, some of which resulted in mortality. This is demonstrated by the age profile of first suicide attempts in our data, and is confirmed with evidence in

Salway et al. (2021). This problem of mortality selection implies that if anything, our results likely underestimate the effect of conversion therapy on having attempted suicide.

Third, the retrospective variables we use may be subject to recall bias – the (in)ability of respondents to accurately report their significant life events retrospectively. We can gauge the presence of recall bias by testing for heaping in the distribution of the age and implied calendar year when the events occurred. Results in Online Appendix B indicate that heaping by age is an issue, but it can be mitigated by looking only at recent life events. The only variable for which recall bias does not appear to be an issue based on the heaping analysis is first suicide attempt, our primary outcome variable. One could explain this with the argument that first suicide attempts are such a traumatic life event that respondents are able to recall their age at the time accurately, even if the event took place many years prior. The lack of heaping in the age distribution for suicide attempts also helps to dispel concerns that instead of a first suicide attempt, people are reporting the age at which they first began to be severely depressed. Our argument that recall bias is not an issue in the case of first suicide attempt is also supported with findings in Beautrais et al. (1997), a study that used parallel reports from subjects and significant others on precipitating factors and suicide attempts and found no evidence of recall bias.

III.C. Empirical Methodology

Isolating the effect of conversion therapy from confounding factors is a difficult task, largely because the reasons for undergoing conversion therapy may also relate to a transgender person's risk of attempting suicide or running away. In particular, a transgender person going to conversion therapy may be predisposed toward attempting suicide when there are risk factors, especially a hostile family environment, that push the person into conversion therapy and also contribute to psychological distress. Although the USTS does include questions about how supportive or hostile the family is now and was in the past, these questions do not specify at what age the support or hostility began. This makes it difficult to separately identify the effect of a hostile family environment from the conversion therapy effect, but in order to obtain policy-relevant estimates, it is important to do so. Moreover, not everyone who enters conversion therapy does so because they have unsupportive parents. Among all USTS respondents who talked about their gender identity with a professional, 18% said that the professional attempted to stop them from being transgender, irrespective of the family environment (James et al., 2016).

If our assertion about risk factors is true, then people who undergo conversion therapy may be more prone to attempting suicide or running away than those who do not. This assertion is confirmed by Figures 1a and 1b, which report unweighted binned scatters of

having attempted suicide or having run away by exposure to hormone therapy over time, where the x axis represents years before and after the start of conversion therapy (which is initiated in year 0). The figures also show the linear regression lines with a discontinuity in year -1 (one year prior to conversion therapy), and the figures compare those who were born in the same calendar year. Figures 1a and 1b show that transgender youth who were exposed to conversion therapy were more likely to attempt suicide or run away than those who were not exposed, before the therapy had even begun. To make matters worse, leading up to their exposure, this difference was *growing*, nullifying any simple comparisons of suicidality by exposure to conversion therapy.

We tackle this selection issue by exploiting variation in the assignment and timing of conversion therapy across the lives of transgender youth in the U.S. As shown in Figures 2a and 2b, the age at which transgender individuals were first treated with conversion therapy and the calendar year in which the conversion therapy occurred both have considerable variation. We use a stacked DID design to exploit this variation. There are three main advantages to the stacked approach. First, stacking eliminates bias from using already-treated units as controls when the timing of exposure is staggered (Goodman-Bacon, 2021). Second, the stacked estimator is efficient and computationally inexpensive relative to alternatives (Gardner, 2022). Third, stacking allows researchers to construct credible control groups for each cohort individually using either theory or data-driven methods such as a synthetic DID approach, thereby reducing bias when exposure is not randomly assigned (Arkhangelsky et al., 2021). This third characteristic is particularly useful as synthetic DID weights eliminate the differential trends pre-exposure in attempting suicide or running away (Figures 1c and 1d).

To ensure that proper comparisons are drawn, our final sample is a ‘stack’ of cohorts. A cohort is defined as one of every combination of age and calendar year of first exposure. Each cohort includes a treated group: all respondents who 1) report being the same age when exposed to conversion therapy, and 2) were also born during the same calendar year. Each cohort also includes a control group: all respondents who were 1) born during the same calendar year as the treated group, and 2) exposed after the event window or never exposed during the period of analysis.¹ Our baseline estimates focus on first exposures between ages 11 and 17, investigating the five years before and five years after. Cohorts with less than fifty control units are dropped, as are cohorts observed less than five years post-exposure, ensuring that composition changes will not create misleading dynamic treatment effects. Within each cohort, time is aligned with exposure, so event-time zero always denotes the first year of

¹To be clear, individuals who meet these conditions for multiple cohorts are included as controls multiple times, and the same individual may appear as a control or as treated in different cohorts. Unlike the control group, an individual can appear as a treated unit only once by design.

conversion therapy. Depending on the outcome, our final sample includes up to 247 cohorts, comprised of 1,078 treated individuals and 24,192 controls, totaling approximately one million observations (again, individuals may appear in multiple cohorts).

This approach ensures that within each cohort, our synthetic DID estimates are robust to both misspecification (Arkhangelsky et al., 2021) and to bias caused by using already-treated units as controls (Goodman-Bacon, 2021). We efficiently aggregate the within-cohort estimates using a stacked DID approach with dynamic treatment effects.² As is standard, we test for selection bias by allowing the trends in the outcome to deviate between the treated and control individuals for five years prior to conversion therapy.³ The baseline specification follows:

$$Y_{c,i,t} = \mu + \sum_{k=-5}^4 \beta_k D_{k,c,i,t} + X'_{c,i,t} \gamma + \alpha_{c,i} + \delta_{c,t} + \epsilon_{c,i,t} \quad (1)$$

where Y denotes an indicator for person i of cohort c for having attempted suicide or run away as of event-time t , D_k are leads and lags of an indicator variable for the year of conversion therapy exposure, X is a vector of the four cohort-specific controls for socially transitioning, $\alpha_{c,i}$ are cohort-specific individual fixed effects, $\delta_{c,t}$ are cohort-specific time fixed effects, and $\epsilon_{c,i,t}$ is the error term. The standard errors are clustered by individual, the level at which the conversion therapy occurs. Note that if we were to cluster by cohort-unit, the stacked difference-in-difference estimates would over-reject the null hypothesis due to inflating the sample size and not accounting for duplication. Hence to account for the sample size change from stacking, the robust standard errors are clustered by individual, not cohort-individual. This clustering strategy is now standard for the stacked procedure.

Because the main identifying assumption is parallel trends in the outcome and our data indicate that we lack parallel trends, we apply Arkhangelsky et al. (2021)'s synthetic unit weights to the control group. This strategy balances the trends in the outcome between treated and control individuals within each cohort. In other words, we re-weight the control individuals in each cohort so that their pre-exposure trends match the treated group. To do so, the procedure designs the unit weights in such a way that the treated units have an average outcome that is more or less parallel with the weighted average of the control units before starting conversion therapy.

One may be concerned that the above DID estimates make a suspect comparison even after reweighting the controls. Indeed, there may be fundamental differences in trends between

²We also provide estimates that manually aggregate the cohort-specific estimates, weighting by the sample share. The stacked estimates are slightly conservative.

³For the overall effect of the conversion therapy, we estimate a separate stacked synthetic DID regression with a single treatment indicator, applying the product of the synthetic unit and synthetic time weights to further reduce bias (Arkhangelsky et al., 2021). These weights are referred to as synthetic DID weights.

transgender youths who undergo conversion therapy and those who do not, or those who do so five or more years later. To address this concern, we repeat this analysis with three important changes: one, we reduce the post-exposure window to one year rather than five years; two, we restrict the control group to individuals who are exposed to conversion therapy when one year older than the treated group; and three, to have enough control units, we allow individuals within cohorts to be born in different calendar years.⁴ If people who are exposed to conversion therapy at similar points in their lives are otherwise similar, then we can credibly estimate the immediate effect of conversion therapy – although the downsides are substantial. We can only estimate the effect of conversion therapy after one year, and our sample size is severely limited. We refer to this second analysis as an event study since all individuals in the sample are exposed to conversion therapy at some point. By limiting the control group to those who successively undergo conversion therapy, the event study approach can estimate the immediate effect of conversion therapy using only variation in the precise timing of exposure, which is plausibly exogenous.

III.D. Covariate Balance

Transgender youth exposed to conversion therapy are different than those who are not, as shown in Table 1. The first two columns display the average pretreatment means by treatment status for the DID sample: youth who underwent to conversion therapy (treated) and youth who did not (control). After reporting the difference between the treated and control groups, the next two columns display the average pretreatment means by treatment status for the one-year event study: people who were exposed to conversion therapy during the event window (treated) and people who were exposed to conversion therapy when one year older (control). To provide a thorough look at the covariate balance, we include the four social transitioning variables, several demographic indicators (race, sex assigned at birth, and region of birth), and several indicators that signal family support and access to resources (court name change, puberty blockers, hormone therapy, and surgical therapy).

Table 1 shows that transgender youth who are exposed to conversion therapy are less likely to be white, assigned male at birth, or born in the Midwest, and they are also more likely to have been born in the South. These differences also hold up for the smaller event study sample but they are not statistically significant. Although there are virtually no differences between the treated and control groups in the indicators of parental support and access to resources,

⁴For the event study sample, a cohort is defined by the age when individuals were first exposed to conversion therapy. So, if the treated group underwent conversion therapy at age 15, then the control group underwent conversion therapy at age 16, regardless of calendar year of birth. The event time is aligned with the age of exposure in each cohort. Since people of the same age may have been born in different calendar years, cohort-calendar year fixed effects are added to the regression specification.

we do observe for both the DID sample and the event study sample that transgender youth who are exposed to conversion therapy are more likely to have socially transitioned (felt their gender was different, thought of themselves as transgender, told another person they were transgender, or lived full-time as their identified gender). This imbalance is perhaps intuitive: knowledge of transgender status is a necessary condition for conversion therapy administration, implying that youth who have socially transitioned may be selected into conversion therapy. To help mitigate selection bias, our baseline regression specification includes the four control variables for social transitioning. We also tackle the issue of drawing comparisons between individuals at similar stages in transitioning with inverse probability weights. The inverse probability weights reweight the control group for each cohort so that the control group is on average at a similar stage in their transition as the treated group is, on average. This claim is evidenced by Online Appendix Figures A.2 – A.9, which show these weights successfully balance the observable characteristics; after applying the weights, the treated group and control group are at similar stages for all respective variables in the survey.

The one-year event study approach further addresses this selection by exploiting variation in the timing of exposure to conversion therapy, which, on a small enough scale, is likely as-good-as-random. The event study sample restricts the control groups to only transgender youth who are exposed to conversion therapy when one year older than the treated groups. This restriction eliminates the demographic and regional imbalance and should mitigate most of the social transitioning differences.

IV. Five-Year Effect of Conversion Therapy: A DID Approach

The main results from the DID approach indicate that conversion therapy has deleterious effects on transgender youth. In particular, our DID estimates associate conversion therapy with a 17.0 (s.e.=1.0) percentage point increase in having attempted suicide and a 7.8 (s.e.=.7) percentage point increase in having run away over the five years following first exposure (Table 2). Relative to the respective pretreatment means of 30.9 and 6.1, these suggest a remarkable increase of 55% in having attempted suicide and 128% in having run away. The estimates are precise, ruling out effects below an increase of 15 percentage points in having attempted suicide and 6 percentage points in having run away at 95% confidence.

The detrimental effects of conversion therapy surface immediately after exposure and accumulate with time (Figure 3), which speaks to the intensification of gender dysphoria and gender minority stress when exposed to a hostile environment. For the five years preceding conversion therapy, the trend in having attempted suicide or run away for those exposed is

indistinguishable from those who are not. During the first year of conversion therapy, the difference in having attempted suicide rises by approximately 12 percentage points and in having run away by about 4 percentage points. After five years, the difference in having attempted suicide rises by approximately 20 percentage points and having run away by about 12 percentage points. These numbers are striking and go a long way to challenge the views of healthcare practitioners, spiritual guides, and conservative politicians who continue to offer conversion therapy or block conversion therapy bans. This practice is clearly harmful, particularly for young people, and our results imply long-run rather than transitory effects.

IV.A. Heterogeneous Effects of Conversion Therapy

We test for heterogeneity in the effect of conversion therapy on attempting suicide or running away by the cohort's age during their first exposure. These estimates provide a falsification test: people who undergo conversion therapy as adults, rather than adolescents, arguably have more agency in the decision. As a consequence, conversion therapy's effect should diminish with adulthood, but not necessarily disappear. Our estimates pass the falsification test: conversion therapy has a much smaller effect on attempting suicide for adults aged 21 or older and does not have any effect on running away (Figure 4). As might be expected, the effect on running away is very small when exposure to conversion therapy started at ages 19-20 and ages 21-22, and then disappears completely due to top-coding running away at age 21, which is discussed in Online Appendix B. In contrast, the effect of conversion therapy is striking for earlier exposures (ages 11 and 12), exceeding a 20-percentage point increase in having attempted suicide. Note that the association of conversion therapy with a first suicide attempt during adulthood may be attenuated because the majority of first suicide attempts among transgender people occur during adolescence. Closely related, the adverse effect of conversion therapy on the extensive margin is the largest at age 11 and 12 (due to fewer 11 or 12-year-olds having previous suicide attempts) even if the overall effect of conversion therapy (increase in the number of suicide attempts) is comparable or even greater in individuals first exposed to conversion therapy at higher ages due to the intensive margin becoming more important for older individuals.

We do not find any evidence of heterogeneity by pretreatment demographics such as race, sex assigned at birth, or region of birth (Figure 5), which shows that conversion therapy is equally bad for everyone and if anything, strengthens our results. A similar analysis also shows there is no evidence of heterogeneity by the calendar year of first exposure to conversion therapy (Online Appendix Figure A.10).

V. The Effect of Conversion Therapy After One Year, an Event Study Approach

As discussed earlier, requests for conversion therapy almost always come from parents and guardians rather than young people themselves. Moreover, adolescents do not have the legal authority to make their own medical decisions, so they often have no choice but to abide by their parents' demands to attend conversion therapy (Byne, 2016). Data from the USTS indicate that 14% of transgender respondents who had come out to their families were forced to go to conversion therapy (James et al., 2016). Because conversion therapy is often administered in the context of transgender children coming out to unsupportive parents, there are fundamental differences between adolescents exposed to conversion therapy and people who are not exposed, or are exposed at a much later age. This would imply that our DID estimates may be capturing both the effects of conversion therapy as well as the effects of living in a hostile family environment. Our event study estimates address this concern by comparing adolescents who undergo conversion therapy with those who undergo conversion therapy one year later, with the assumption that the exact timing of conversion therapy is as-good-as-random. Hence the covariates of the adolescents we are comparing are more similar in this event study compared to the DID approach since they have all undergone conversion therapy and have done so within a relatively small window of time. The downsides to this approach are that we can only estimate the effect of conversion therapy one-year post treatment, and the sample size is limited.

Conversion therapy is again found to be detrimental to the mental health and wellbeing of transgender youth (Table 3 and Figure 6). For the five years preceding conversion therapy, the trend in having attempted suicide or run away between the treated and controls groups are indistinguishable. There is an abrupt change following conversion therapy. During the first year of conversion therapy, the difference in having attempted suicide rises by 4.9 percentage points and having run away by 2.8 percentage points relative to transgender adolescents who will be exposed when one year older. Relative to the pretreatment means of 35.6 and 5.9 respectively, we associate conversion therapy with an immediate 13.8% increase in attempting suicide and a 47.5% increase in running away.

The event study estimates are around half the size of the first year of the dynamic DID estimates that we had reported in Figure 3, thus indicating that the DID estimates were indeed capturing some effects of socially transitioning in a hostile family environment. That said, the DID estimates still provide compelling evidence for the importance of supportive environments for the mental health and wellbeing of transgender youth. They also suggest that the effect of conversion therapy not only persists, but also grows with time; an insight

we cannot assess with our event study approach.

VI. Robustness Checks

We subject the DID and the event study results to a battery of robustness tests. The estimates hold using alternative regression specifications, such as the controlling for legal name changes, medical transitioning (puberty blockers, hormone therapy, and surgical therapy); they hold without using synthetic DID weights; and they hold with cohort-individual-specific linear time trends (Online Appendix Tables A.1 and A.2). We also address the issue of drawing comparisons between individuals at similar stages in transitioning with inverse probability weights. The inverse probability weights reweight the control group for each cohort so that the control group is on average at a similar stage in their transition as the treated group is, on average. This claim is evidenced by Appendix Figures A.2 – A.9, which show these weights successfully balance the observable characteristics; after applying the weights, the treated group and control group are at similar stages for all respective variables in the survey. Online Appendix Tables A.1 and A.2 show that both the DID and event study estimates do not meaningfully change when using these weights.

The DID and event study estimates are also robust to alternative choices made when constructing the stacked sample, such as the number of post-treatment years (Online Appendix Table A.3) or the minimum number of control units required for a cohort to be included in the sample (Online Appendix Table A.4). Most notably, our sample drops individuals who started conversion therapy before age 11. To test the robustness of using a different starting age, we conducted robustness checks that use alternative age thresholds (ages 9, 10, 11, 12, and 13) for the minimum age at which the treated group of each cohort started conversion therapy. Results for the DID estimates are found in Appendix Table A.5 and for the event study estimates in Appendix Table A.6. These alternative starting points make very little difference, likely because there are so few treated observations in these younger cohorts

The stacked DID estimator may be inconsistent for the sample average treatment effect on the treated (ATT) when there is heterogeneity in treatment effects across cohorts or time, caused by weighting by both the variance of treatment and sample share within each cohort, rather than by only the sample share (Baker et al., 2022; Gardner, 2022). When we manually aggregate the cohort-specific estimates, weighting by only the sample share, both the estimates and standard errors are virtually unchanged, alleviating any such concerns (Online Appendix Tables A.7 and A.8).

The histograms provided in Online Appendix B show that heaping by age is an issue,

but it can be mitigated by looking only at recent life events, indicating that recall bias may be less concerning when events are recent. We hence test the robustness of our estimates to incrementally omitting cohorts by the number of years before the survey that they first had conversion therapy (Appendix Table A.9). Our difference-in-difference estimates hold at all thresholds, even if we only consider cohorts that experienced conversion therapy five years before the survey, which is the strictest cutoff possible given our five-year event window, providing some assurance about recall bias affecting the results. However, the effect on running away does become statistically insignificant at the strictest threshold due to a small sample size.

In another robustness check, we attempt to disentangle the effect of conversion therapy from a hostile family environment. To do so, we estimate our baseline difference-in-difference specification using only respondents who report either having a supportive family environment, or do not report any form of family rejection for being trans, or both, in Online Appendix Table A.10. We also do this for our event study in Online Appendix Table A.11. This procedure is especially important for the difference-in-difference estimates because they primarily compare respondents who started conversion therapy to those who never will, which may not adequately account for differences in family support. This is the main explanation we have for why the first year of the dynamic difference-in-difference estimates is different than the one-year event study estimate.

Under a strong assumption that we can correctly identify respondents who have had a supportive family for their entire past, these estimates provide the effect of conversion therapy independent of family support on attempting suicide or running away for this group. As perhaps expected, the difference-in-difference estimates are smaller for these subgroups, although the estimates are still very large and precise, suggesting that conversion therapy may meaningfully affect the mental health of recipients independently of the family support mechanism. In contrast, the magnitude of the event study estimates is similar across subgroups, but statistical significance is sometimes lost, likely from the small sample sizes. A generous interpretation of these results is that the event study estimates control for differences in family support by using only the precise timing of conversion therapy, whereas the difference-in-difference estimates primarily compare those who have conversion therapy to those who never will, allowing for large differences in family support.

We also provide estimates that drop respondents with life events concurrent with conversion therapy. We provide the difference-in-difference estimate for this subsample in Column 5 of Online Appendix Table A.10. We also provide the event study estimate for this subsample in Column 5 of Online Appendix Table A.11. To create the subsample, we drop respondents who report starting conversion therapy at the same age as another retrospective life event,

which include the following: 1) Felt their gender was different, 2) Thought of themselves as transgender, 3) Told others transgender, 4) Full-time as gender different than the one assigned at birth, 5) Went to court for legal name change, 6) Starting puberty blocking hormones, 7) Starting hormone treatment, 8) First surgery for gender transition. The difference-in-difference estimate for attempting suicide or running away is virtually unchanged, as is the event study estimate for running away. However, the event study estimates for attempting suicide slightly diminishes and is only statistically significant at 10% confidence.

Finally, to explore the extent to which our other retrospective variables correlate with the timing of conversion therapy, we conducted regressions in which the outcome is the conversion therapy dummy variable. The predictors include all variables that we have time variant information other than our two outcomes (attempted suicide and running away). The predictors include the following: ever felt gender was different than assigned sex at birth, ever thought of themselves as transgender, ever told other they are trans, lives full-time as identified gender, went to court for legal name change, used puberty blocked, used hormone therapy, and had surgery for gender transition. The regressions use the stacked event study sample, implying that the regression coefficients measure the correlation between the variable and the timing of conversion therapy. As shown in Appendix Table A.12, the regression coefficients indicate that the social transitioning measures are highly correlated with the timing of conversion therapy. However, our synthetic unit weights substantially diminish the magnitude of the correlation. Moreover, the inverse probability weights successfully eliminate the correlation for all of these variables other than having surgery or going to court for a legal name change, which are both extremely rare in the youth sample.

VII. Discussion

This study has used the 2015 U.S. Transgender Survey to test how exposure to conversion therapy affects the risk of attempting suicide and running away from home among transgender adolescents. We constructed a retrospective panel of transgender youth and employed a stacked DID design to show that exposure to conversion therapy substantially increases the risk that a transgender adolescent will try to commit suicide or run away. The ATT of conversion therapy on having attempted suicide is an increase of 17 percentage points, which constitutes a 55% increase in the risk of attempting suicide relative to the average rate of suicide attempts. Moreover, the ATT on the likelihood of running away is an increase of 7.8 percentage points, which represents more than doubling in the risk of running away relative to the sample average. These effects are largest when exposure to conversion therapy occurs at a

young age, and they not only persist but also grow with time. Although we are constrained by some formidable data and methodology limitations (especially the challenge of disentangling exposure to conversion therapy from growing up in a hostile family environment), we believe that the DID estimates provide strong evidence for the adverse effects of conversion therapy on the mental health and wellbeing of transgender youth.

Our estimates bolster the argument regarding the importance of parents accepting their children's gender identity and supporting their children rather than subjecting them to conversion therapy. Not only is the conversion therapy counterproductive, but it can also have adverse effects on even the most extreme expressions of depression, distress, and hopelessness. Given that parents and guardians are the primary agents who pressure adolescents into enrolling in conversion therapy, an important policy recommendation is to provide more professional support and counseling services for parents of transgender children. In addition, healthcare providers and religious counselors need training opportunities for providing gender-affirmative approaches in their practices and institutional settings. This study also informs policy makers about the potential benefits of implementing legal bans in states where conversion therapy is still practiced. Making conversion therapy obsolete can help to reinforce the message that this practice is both unethical and harmful.

Our results build on previous evidence showing that transgender individuals living in states with more protective legislation for transgender people and anti-discrimination are better off, with a greater likelihood of seeking healthcare (Goldenberg et al., 2020). Taking steps to bolster the welfare of transgender youth matters not only for individual wellbeing, it also matters for society at large and the macroeconomy. In particular, suicides entail not only extremely high emotional and social costs, but also losses in human capital and labor productivity. For example, evidence in Rivera et al. (2017) indicates that in 2013, Spain's economy lost 38,038 potential years of working life due to suicide deaths, which cost the overall economy an estimated 565 million Euro (roughly US\$ 425 million at the time). In the U.S., economic supports (through a higher minimum wage and earned income tax credits) are estimated to reduce suicides by 13,600 per year among low-educated working-age adults, which could contribute to an increase of \$1.1 billion annually in worker productivity (Dow et al., 2020).

Workplace losses due to disability arising from depression are also high, with the implication that efforts to improve the mental health of transgender youth may contribute to less absenteeism, greater work productivity, and higher labor force participation (Lerner and Henke, 2008; Chatterji et al., 2011). More broadly, laws that promote inclusiveness of sexual orientation and gender identity minorities have repercussions for overall macroeconomic growth. Estimates in Badgett et al. (2019) indicate that adding an additional legal right for

LGBT individuals related to anti-discrimination, social rights, and family law can boost a country's overall GDP/capita by approximately \$2000. As such, in the long run, taking steps to reduce the risk that transgender youth attempt suicide may have substantial repercussions that go far beyond mental health.

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Figure 1: Binned Scatter Plots of Attempting Suicide or Running Away by Treatment Status

(a) Attempted suicide (unweighted)

(b) Ran away (unweighted)

(c) Attempted suicide (synthetic unit weights)

(d) Ran away (synthetic unit weights)

Notes: Figures 1a and 1b report unweighted binned scatters of attempted suicide or ran away by exposure to hormone therapy. Figures 1c and 1d apply synthetic unit weights to the control group. All figures also show the linear regression lines with a discontinuity one year prior to conversion therapy. The control group includes both people who never report having conversion therapy and people who are exposed to conversion therapy after the five-year event window. The binned averages are found by averaging the outcome by treatment status and event time using our baseline stacked sample.

Figure 2: Distribution of the Age and Year of First Exposure to Conversion Therapy.

(a) Age when treated with conversion therapy

(b) Year when treated with conversion therapy

Notes: The figures depict variation in the timing of conversion therapy in our baseline analysis sample. Figure 2a is a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they were first treated with conversion therapy. Figure 2b is a histogram depicting the distribution of the calendar year of conversion therapy treatment. Respondents who were never treated with conversion therapy are omitted, as are those treated before age 11. The data for conversion therapy comes from the following question: How old were you the first time a professional tried to make you identify only with your sex assigned at birth (in other words, try to stop you being trans)?

Figure 3: Evolution of the Effect of Conversion Therapy on the Risk of Attempting Suicide and Running Away for Transgender Youth.

(a) Attempted suicide (percentage point change)

(b) Ran away (percentage point change)

Notes: The figures show the estimates of the stacked DID model given by Equation 1. The outcome used in Figure 3a is a dummy variable for attempting suicide (zero before the age of first attempting suicide and, if ever, 1 after) and Figure 3b is dummy variable for running away (zero before the age of running away and, if ever, 1 after). All specifications include cohort-individual and cohort-time fixed effects as well as cohort-specific controls for socially transitioning, and are weighted by synthetic unit weights. The shaded area in each figure is the 95% confidence interval based on robust standard errors clustered by individual.

Figure 4: Heterogeneity by Age at Exposure in the Effect of Conversion Therapy on the Risk of Attempting Suicide and Running Away for Transgender People.

(a) Heterogeneity by age (attempted suicide)

(b) Heterogeneity by age (ran away)

Notes: This figure depicts the baseline DID estimate for the overall effect of conversion therapy on the probability of attempting suicide or running away, subsetting by the cohort's age when the treated group was first exposed to conversion therapy. The y-axis is the percentage point change in the outcome, and the x-axis is the subset used for the estimate. The blue bars in each figure depict the group specific estimate and the red bands depict 95% confidence intervals based on robust standard errors clustered at the individual level. All regressions include cohort-individual and cohort-time fixed effects as well as cohort-specific controls for socially transitioning, and are weighted by synthetic unit weights.

Figure 5: Heterogeneity by Pre-Treatment Demographics in the Effect of Conversion Therapy on the Risk of Attempting Suicide and Running Away for Transgender Youth.

(a) Heterogeneity by year (attempted suicide)

(b) Heterogeneity by year (ran away)

Notes: This figure depicts the baseline DID estimate for the overall effect of conversion therapy on the probability of attempting suicide or running away, interacting the treatment indicator with pre-treatment demographics. The blue diamonds are the point estimates. The pink bars are the 95% confidence interval based on standard errors that are clustered by individual. Synthetic unit weights are applied. Point estimates and standard errors, in parentheses, are reported on the second y-axis. All regressions include cohort-individual and cohort-time fixed effects and include cohort-specific controls for socially transitioning.

Figure 6: Event Study Estimates of the Effect of Conversion Therapy on the Risk of Attempting Suicide and Running Away for Transgender People.

(a) Attempted suicide (percentage point change)

(b) Ran away (percentage point change)

Notes: The figures show the estimates of the stacked event study model. For each cohort, the control group includes only respondents who report being exposed to conversion therapy one year after the treated group was exposed. The outcome used in Figure 6a is a dummy variable for attempting suicide (zero before the age of first attempting suicide and, if ever, 1 after) and Figure 6b is dummy variable for ever having run away (zero before the age of running away and, if ever, 1 after). All regressions include cohort-individual fixed effects, cohort-age fixed effects, cohort-calender year fixed effects, cohort-specific controls for socially transitioning, and are weighted by synthetic unit weights. The shaded area in each figure is the 95% confidence interval based on robust standard errors clustered by individual.

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Table 1: Covariate Balance Between the Treated and Control Groups Prior to Conversion Therapy

	Difference-in-differences sample			Event study sample		
	Treated	Control	Difference	Treated	Control	Difference
Felt gender different	.850	.711	.139*** (.010)	.836	.796	.040*** (.005)
Thought transgender	.537	.363	.174*** (.014)	.530	.463	.067*** (.006)
Told others trans	.192	.079	.113*** (.011)	.188	.146	.042*** (.005)
Full time as identity	.026	.012	.014** (.004)	.033	.026	.007** (.002)
Court name change	.000	.000	-.000 (.000)	.000	.000	.000 (.000)
Had puberty blockers	.001	.000	.000 (.000)	.001	.000	.001 (.001)
Had hormone therapy	.001	.001	-.000 (.000)	.001	.000	.001* (.000)
Had surgical therapy	.002	.000	.001 (.001)	.002	.001	.001 (.001)
White	.792	.824	-.032* (.013)	.783	.786	-.003 (.006)
Assigned male at birth	.392	.545	-.152*** (.016)	.359	.369	-.010 (.007)
<i>Region of birth</i>						
Northeast	.220	.224	-.004 (.014)	.220	.222	-.002 (.006)
Midwest	.200	.250	-.049*** (.014)	.205	.215	-.010 (.006)
South	.276	.237	.039** (.014)	.281	.274	.007 (.006)
West	.253	.237	.016 (.014)	.242	.236	.006 (.006)
Other	.000	.000	.000 (.000)	.000	.000	.000 (.000)
$F_{15, 1544}$			27.6***			12.9***
People	1,078	24,141		1,313	1,495	

Notes: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. This table displays average pretreatment means by treatment status: youth who underwent to conversion therapy (treated) and youth who did not (control). Robust standard errors are clustered by individual and reported in parenthesis. The row F statistics reports the joint F-test for the difference in means. The control units are weighted by the synthetic unit weights.

Table 2: DID Estimates for the Average Five-Year Effect of Conversion Therapy on Attempting Suicide or Running Away for Transgender Youth.

	(1)	(2)
Outcome:	Attempted suicide	Ran away
Effect of conversion therapy	.170*** (.010)	.078*** (.007)
Pre-treatment average outcome	.309	.061
Treated individuals	1,078	935
Control individuals	24,192	17,921
Number of cohorts	247	231
Observations	1,044,120	709,177
Cohort-individual fixed effects	✓	✓
Cohort-time fixed effects	✓	✓
Social transition controls	✓	✓

Notes: $*p < 0.05$, $**p < 0.01$, $***p < 0.001$. This table reports the baseline DID estimates for exposure to conversion therapy. A separate cohort is defined for every combination of age and calendar year of first exposure. The event window includes five years before and after each cohort's exposure. For each cohort, the control group includes all individuals are 1) born during the same calendar year as the treated group, and 2) exposed after the event window or never exposed during the sample. Cohorts with less than fifty control units are dropped. All regressions include cohort-individual and cohort-time fixed effects as well as cohort-specific controls for socially transitioning, and are weighted by synthetic unit weights. Robust standard errors are clustered by individual and reported in parenthesis.

Table 3: Event Study Estimates for the Average One-Year Effect of Conversion Therapy on Attempting Suicide or Running Away for Transgender Youth.

	(1)	(2)
Outcome:	Attempted suicide	Ran away
Effect of conversion therapy	.049*** (.014)	.028** (.009)
Pre-treatment average outcome	.356	.059
Treated individuals	1,313	1,133
Control individuals	1,495	1,289
Number of cohorts	7	7
Observations	11,434	9,064
Cohort-individual fixed effects	✓	✓
Cohort-age fixed effects	✓	✓
Cohort-year fixed effects	✓	✓
Social transition controls	✓	✓

Notes: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. This table reports the baseline event study estimates for exposure to conversion therapy. A separate cohort is defined for every age of first exposure. The event window includes five years prior to each cohort's exposure, and one year after. For each cohort, the control group includes respondents who are report being exposed to conversion therapy one year after the treated group. All regressions include cohort-individual fixed effects, cohort-age fixed effects, cohort-calendar year fixed effects, cohort-specific controls for socially transitioning, and are weighted by synthetic unit weights. Robust standard errors are clustered by individual and reported in parenthesis.

A. Online Appendix – Additional Tables and Figures

Figure A.1: Map of the Share of Respondents Who Had Conversion Therapy by State of Birth

Notes: The figures maps the share of respondents by state of birth who answered yes to the question, “Did any professional (such as a psychologist, counselor, religious advisor) try to make you identify only with your sex assigned at birth (in other words, try to stop you being trans)?” Respondents who were not asked the question or did not answer are omitted. The USTS survey weights are applied, accounting for oversampling by race and of 18 year olds. The color thresholds are determined by quantile.

Figure A.2: Binned Scatter Plots of Ever Feeling Gender was Different by Conversion Therapy Status

Notes: The figure depicts binned means, averaging the outcome by treatment status and event time using our baseline stacked event study sample. The dots depict the average outcome each year relative to the year that the treated group starts conversion therapy; the control group starts conversion therapy one year later. Red denotes the treated group's averages (unweighted), green denotes the control group's averages (unweighted), and blue also denotes the control group's averages applying inverse probability weights. These weights balance the following time variant observable characteristics pre- and post-treatment: felt gender was different, thought of themselves as trans, told others they are trans, lives full-time as gender, went to court for name change, started hormone therapy, used puberty blockers, had surgery for transition. The figure also shows the linear regression lines fit prior to conversion therapy for each group, and the dashed line extends the fitted line into the post-treatment window.

Figure A.3: Binned Scatter Plots of Ever Thought of Themselves as Trans by Conversion Therapy Status

Notes: The figure depicts binned means, averaging the outcome by treatment status and event time using our baseline stacked event study sample. The dots depict the average outcome each year relative to the year that the treated group starts conversion therapy; the control group starts conversion therapy one year later. Red denotes the treated group's averages (unweighted), green denotes the control group's averages (unweighted), and blue also denotes the control group's averages applying inverse probability weights. These weights balance the following time variant observable characteristics pre- and post-treatment: felt gender was different, thought of themselves as trans, told others they are trans, lives full-time as gender, went to court for name change, started hormone therapy, used puberty blockers, had surgery for transition. The figure also shows the linear regression lines fit prior to conversion therapy for each group, and the dashed line extends the fitted line into the post-treatment window.

Figure A.4: Binned Scatter Plots of Ever Told Others They are Trans by Conversion Therapy Status

Notes: The figure depicts binned means, averaging the outcome by treatment status and event time using our baseline stacked event study sample. The dots depict the average outcome each year relative to the year that the treated group starts conversion therapy; the control group starts conversion therapy one year later. Red denotes the treated group's averages (unweighted), green denotes the control group's averages (unweighted), and blue also denotes the control group's averages applying inverse probability weights. These weights balance the following time variant observable characteristics pre- and post-treatment: felt gender was different, thought of themselves as trans, told others they are trans, lives full-time as gender, went to court for name change, started hormone therapy, used puberty blockers, had surgery for transition. The figure also shows the linear regression lines fit prior to conversion therapy for each group, and the dashed line extends the fitted line into the post-treatment window.

Figure A.5: Binned Scatter Plots of Ever Lived Full-Time as Gender by Conversion Therapy Status

Notes: The figure depicts binned means, averaging the outcome by treatment status and event time using our baseline stacked event study sample. The dots depict the average outcome each year relative to the year that the treated group starts conversion therapy; the control group starts conversion therapy one year later. Red denotes the treated group's averages (unweighted), green denotes the control group's averages (unweighted), and blue also denotes the control group's averages applying inverse probability weights. These weights balance the following time variant observable characteristics pre- and post-treatment: felt gender was different, thought of themselves as trans, told others they are trans, lives full-time as gender, went to court for name change, started hormone therapy, used puberty blockers, had surgery for transition. The figure also shows the linear regression lines fit prior to conversion therapy for each group, and the dashed line extends the fitted line into the post-treatment window.

Figure A.6: Binned Scatter Plots of Ever Went to Court for Legal Name Change by Conversion Therapy Status

Notes: The figure depicts binned means, averaging the outcome by treatment status and event time using our baseline stacked event study sample. The dots depict the average outcome each year relative to the year that the treated group starts conversion therapy; the control group starts conversion therapy one year later. Red denotes the treated group's averages (unweighted), green denotes the control group's averages (unweighted), and blue also denotes the control group's averages applying inverse probability weights. These weights balance the following time variant observable characteristics pre- and post-treatment: felt gender was different, thought of themselves as trans, told others they are trans, lives full-time as gender, went to court for name change, started hormone therapy, used puberty blockers, had surgery for transition. The figure also shows the linear regression lines fit prior to conversion therapy for each group, and the dashed line extends the fitted line into the post-treatment window.

Figure A.7: Binned Scatter Plots of Ever Used Puberty Blockers by Conversion Therapy Status

Notes: The figure depicts binned means, averaging the outcome by treatment status and event time using our baseline stacked event study sample. The dots depict the average outcome each year relative to the year that the treated group starts conversion therapy; the control group starts conversion therapy one year later. Red denotes the treated group’s averages (unweighted), green denotes the control group’s averages (unweighted), and blue also denotes the control group’s averages applying inverse probability weights. These weights balance the following time variant observable characteristics pre- and post-treatment: felt gender was different, thought of themselves as trans, told others they are trans, lives full-time as gender, went to court for name change, started hormone therapy, used puberty blockers, had surgery for transition. The figure also shows the linear regression lines fit prior to conversion therapy for each group, and the dashed line extends the fitted line into the post-treatment window.

Figure A.8: Binned Scatter Plots of Ever Started Hormone Therapy by Conversion Therapy Status

Notes: The figure depicts binned means, averaging the outcome by treatment status and event time using our baseline stacked event study sample. The dots depict the average outcome each year relative to the year that the treated group starts conversion therapy; the control group starts conversion therapy one year later. Red denotes the treated group's averages (unweighted), green denotes the control group's averages (unweighted), and blue also denotes the control group's averages applying inverse probability weights. These weights balance the following time variant observable characteristics pre- and post-treatment: felt gender was different, thought of themselves as trans, told others they are trans, lives full-time as gender, went to court for name change, started hormone therapy, used puberty blockers, had surgery for transition. The figure also shows the linear regression lines fit prior to conversion therapy for each group, and the dashed line extends the fitted line into the post-treatment window.

Figure A.9: Binned Scatter Plots of Ever Had Surgery for Gender Transition by Conversion Therapy Status

Notes: The figure depicts binned means, averaging the outcome by treatment status and event time using our baseline stacked event study sample. The dots depict the average outcome each year relative to the year that the treated group starts conversion therapy; the control group starts conversion therapy one year later. Red denotes the treated group's averages (unweighted), green denotes the control group's averages (unweighted), and blue also denotes the control group's averages applying inverse probability weights. These weights balance the following time variant observable characteristics pre- and post-treatment: felt gender was different, thought of themselves as trans, told others they are trans, lives full-time as gender, went to court for name change, started hormone therapy, used puberty blockers, had surgery for transition. The figure also shows the linear regression lines fit prior to conversion therapy for each group, and the dashed line extends the fitted line into the post-treatment window.

Figure A.10: Heterogeneity by Calendar Year of Exposure in the Effect of Conversion Therapy on the Risk of Attempting Suicide and Running Away for Transgender Youth.

(a) Heterogeneity by year (attempted suicide)

(b) Heterogeneity by year (ran away)

Notes: This figure depicts the baseline DID estimate for the overall effect of conversion therapy on the probability of attempting suicide or running away, subsetting by the calendar year when the cohort was first exposed. The group 1953-63 includes a greater number of years because of the small sample size. The y-axis is the percentage point change in the outcome, and the x-axis is the subset used for the estimate. The blue bars in each figure depict the group specific estimate and the red bands depict 95% confidence intervals based on robust standard errors clustered at the individual level. All regressions include cohort-individual and cohort-time fixed effects as well as cohort-specific controls for socially transitioning, and are weighted by synthetic unit weights.

Table A.1: Robustness of Five-Year Difference-in-Differences Estimates to Specification.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4) (baseline)	(5)	(6)
<i>Attempted suicide</i>						
Effect of conversion therapy	.212*** (.012)	.171*** (.013)	.181*** (.011)	.170*** (.010)	.172*** (.010)	.172*** (.010)
Pre-treatment average outcome	.309	.309	.309	.309	.309	.309
Observations	1,347,840	490,810	1,044,121	1,044,120	1,044,064	1,044,064
<i>Ran away</i>						
Effect of conversion therapy	.131*** (.010)	.106*** (.010)	.107*** (.009)	.078*** (.007)	.078*** (.007)	.078*** (.007)
Pre-treatment average outcome	.061	.061	.061	.061	.061	.061
Observations	1,000,090	332,780	709,185	709,177	709,125	709,125
Cohort-individual fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Cohort-time fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Inverse probability weights		✓				
Synthetic diff-in-diff weights			✓	✓	✓	✓
Social transition controls				✓	✓	✓
Medical transition controls					✓	✓
Court name change control					✓	✓
Cohort-individual linear time trends						✓

Notes: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. This table reports the baseline DID estimates for exposure to conversion therapy in Column 1, and tests the robustness to alternative specifications in the remaining columns. Robust standard errors are clustered by individual and reported in parenthesis. The social transition controls are indicators for feeling gender is different, thinking of self as transgender, telling others they are transgender, living as identified gender full time, and obtaining a court name change. Medical transition controls are indicators for puberty blockers, hormone therapy, and surgical therapy.

Table A.2: Robustness of One-Year Event Study Estimates to Specification.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4) (baseline)	(5)	(6)
<i>Attempted suicide</i>						
Effect of conversion therapy	.069*** (.011)	.056*** (.014)	.056*** (.014)	.049*** (.014)	.047*** (.014)	.047*** (.014)
Pre-treatment average outcome	.356	.356	.356	.356	.356	.356
Observations	16,831	16,717	11,434	11,434	11,432	11,432
<i>Ran away</i>						
Effect of conversion therapy	.044*** (.008)	.047*** (.009)	.034*** (.008)	.028** (.009)	.029** (.009)	.029** (.009)
Pre-treatment average outcome	.059	.059	.059	.059	.059	.059
Observations	14,519	14,417	9,064	9,064	9,061	9,061
Cohort-individual fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Cohort-age fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Cohort-year fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Inverse probability weights		✓				
Synthetic diff-in-diff weights			✓	✓	✓	✓
Social transition controls				✓	✓	✓
Medical transition controls					✓	✓
Court name change control					✓	✓
Cohort-individual linear time trends						✓

Notes: $*p < 0.05$, $**p < 0.01$, $***p < 0.001$. This table reports the baseline DID estimates for exposure to conversion therapy in Column 1, and tests the robustness of the estimate to alternative specifications in the remaining columns. Robust standard errors are clustered by individual and reported in parenthesis. The social transition controls are indicators for feeling gender is different, thinking of self as transgender, telling others they are transgender, living as identified gender full time, and obtaining a court name change. Medical transition controls are indicators for puberty blockers, hormone therapy, and surgical therapy.

Table A.3: Robustness of Difference-in-Differences Estimates to the Number of Post-Treatment Years.

	(1)	(2)	(3) (baseline)	(4)	(5)
Years included post-policy:	1	3	5	7	9
<i>Attempted suicide</i>					
Effect of conversion therapy	.107*** (.010)	.145*** (.010)	.170*** (.010)	.187*** (.011)	.196*** (.012)
Pre-treatment average outcome	.356	.350	.309	.272	.249
Observations	611,558	874,047	1,044,120	1,135,235	1,134,281
<i>Ran away</i>					
Effect of conversion therapy	.041*** (.006)	.064*** (.006)	.078*** (.007)	.091*** (.008)	.099*** (.009)
Pre-treatment average outcome	.058	.058	.061	.067	.068
Observations	391,072	582,244	709,177	782,996	790,174
Cohort-individual fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Cohort-time fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Social transition controls	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Notes: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. This table reports the baseline DID estimates for exposure to conversion therapy in Column 3, and tests the robustness to alternative number of years included in the post policy period. All regressions include cohort-individual and cohort-time fixed effects as well as cohort-specific controls for socially transitioning, and are weighted by synthetic DID weights. Robust standard errors are clustered by individual and reported in parenthesis.

Table A.4: Robustness of Five-Year Difference-in-Differences Estimates to the Minimum Number of Control Units.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4) (baseline)	(5)
Minimum number of controls:	20	30	40	50	60
<i>Attempted suicide</i>					
Effect of conversion therapy	.169*** (.010)	.170*** (.010)	.170*** (.010)	.170*** (.010)	.169*** (.010)
Pre-treatment average outcome	.309	.309	.309	.309	.309
Observations	1,044,246	1,044,120	1,044,120	1,044,120	1,043,250
<i>Ran away</i>					
Effect of conversion therapy	.078*** (.007)	.078*** (.007)	.078*** (.007)	.078*** (.007)	.078*** (.007)
Pre-treatment average outcome	.061	.061	.061	.061	.061
Observations	709,429	709,429	709,177	709,177	708,817
Cohort-individual fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Cohort-time fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Social transition controls	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Notes: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. This table reports the baseline DID estimates for exposure to conversion therapy in Column 3, and tests the robustness to using alternative thresholds for the minimum number of control units in the remaining columns. All regressions include cohort-individual and cohort-time fixed effects as well as cohort-specific controls for socially transitioning, and are weighted by synthetic DID weights. Robust standard errors are clustered by individual and reported in parenthesis.

Table A.5: Robustness of Five-Year Difference-in-Differences Estimates to Alternative Age Thresholds.

	(1)	(2)	(3) (baseline)	(4)	(5)
Minimum age threshold:	9	10	11	12	13
<i>Attempted suicide</i>					
Effect of conversion therapy	.170*** (.010)	.170*** (.010)	.170*** (.010)	.172*** (.011)	.151*** (.012)
Pre-treatment average outcome	.292	.297	.309	.319	.339
Observations	1,231,555	1,155,416	1,044,120	922,320	752,249
<i>Ran away</i>					
Effect of conversion therapy	.073*** (.006)	.073*** (.007)	.078*** (.007)	.083*** (.008)	.079*** (.008)
Pre-treatment average outcome	.057	.058	.061	.063	.061
Observations	839,754	783,938	709,177	626,530	521,547
Cohort-individual fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Cohort-time fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Social transition controls	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Notes: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. This table reports the baseline DID estimates for exposure to conversion therapy in Column 3, and tests the robustness to using alternative thresholds for the minimum age the treated group of each cohort must have stated conversion therapy. All regressions include cohort-individual and cohort-time fixed effects as well as cohort-specific controls for socially transitioning, and are weighted by synthetic DID weights. Robust standard errors are clustered by individual and reported in parenthesis.

Table A.6: Robustness of One-Year Event Study Estimates to Alternative Age Thresholds.

	(1)	(2)	(3) (baseline)	(4)	(5)
Minimum age threshold:	9	10	11	12	13
<i>Attempted suicide</i>					
Effect of conversion therapy	.044** (.016)	.045** (.015)	.049*** (.014)	.056*** (.014)	.039** (.014)
Pre-treatment average outcome	.339	.344	.356	.366	.386
Observations	11,974	11,743	11,434	10,730	9,226
<i>Ran away</i>					
Effect of conversion therapy	.028** (.009)	.028** (.009)	.028** (.009)	.033*** (.010)	.030** (.010)
Pre-treatment average outcome	.059	.059	.059	.061	.059
Observations	9,064	9,064	9,064	8,483	7,719
Cohort-individual fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Cohort-age fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Cohort-year fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Social transition controls	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Notes: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. This table reports the baseline event study estimates for exposure to conversion therapy in Column 3, and tests the robustness to using alternative thresholds for the minimum age the treated group of each cohort must have stated conversion therapy. All regressions include cohort-individual and cohort-time fixed effects as well as cohort-specific controls for socially transitioning, and are weighted by synthetic DID weights. Robust standard errors are clustered by individual and reported in parenthesis. Note that the outcome ever running away is relatively has relatively more missing observations than attempting suicide, using a threshold of 9 or 10 years does not increase the number of cohorts for ran away, as these cohorts do not meet the requirement of having 50 unique control individuals for this outcome.

Table A.7: Robustness of Five-Year Difference-in-Differences Estimates to Estimator.

	(1) (baseline)	(2)
Estimator:	Stacked	Manual
<i>Attempted suicide</i>		
Effect of conversion therapy	.170*** (.010)	.169*** (.010)
Pre-treatment average outcome	.309	.309
Observations	1,044,120	1,044,120
<i>Ran away</i>		
Effect of conversion therapy	.078*** (.007)	.085*** (.007)
Pre-treatment average outcome	.061	.061
Observations	709,177	709,177
Cohort-individual fixed effects	✓	✓
Cohort-time fixed effects	✓	✓
Social transition controls	✓	✓

Notes: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. This table reports the baseline DID estimates for exposure to conversion therapy in Column 1. The baseline estimates use stacked DID meaning that OLS is used to average the cohort specific estimates, which weights by both the sample share and variance of treatment. In Column 2, we simultaneously estimate the cohort-specific treatment effects (a single regression using the same stacked dataset), then manually average the cohort-specific regression coefficients using the Stata command `lincom`, weighting only by the sample share of the cohort. Both regressions include cohort-individual and cohort-time fixed effects as well as cohort-specific controls for socially transitioning, and are weighted by synthetic DID weights. Robust standard errors are clustered by individual and reported in parenthesis.

Table A.8: Robustness of One-Year Event Study Estimates to Estimator.

	(1)	(2)
	(baseline)	
Estimator:	Stacked	Manual
<i>Attempted suicide</i>		
Effect of conversion therapy	.049*** (.014)	.043*** (.012)
Pre-treatment average outcome	.356	.356
Observations	11,434	11,464
<i>Ran away</i>		
Effect of conversion therapy	.028** (.009)	.028*** (.008)
Pre-treatment average outcome	.059	.059
Observations	9,064	9,106
Cohort-individual fixed effects	✓	✓
Cohort-age fixed effects	✓	✓
Cohort-year fixed effects	✓	✓
Social transition controls	✓	✓

Notes: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. This table reports the baseline event study estimates for exposure to conversion therapy in Column 1. The baseline estimates use stacked DID meaning that OLS is used to average the cohort specific estimates, which weights by both the sample share and variance of treatment. In Column 2, we simultaneously estimate the cohort-specific treatment effects (a single regression using the same stacked dataset), then manually average the cohort-specific regression coefficients using the Stata command `lincom`, weighting only by the sample share of the cohort. All regressions include cohort-individual and cohort-time fixed effects as well as cohort-specific controls for socially transitioning, and are weighted by synthetic DID weights. Robust standard errors are clustered by individual and reported in parenthesis.

Table A.9: Robustness of Five-Year Difference-in-Differences Estimates to Using Only Cohorts First Exposed to Conversion Therapy Recently.

	(1) (baseline)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Years since treatment cutoff:	Full	30	20	10	5
<i>Attempted suicide</i>					
Effect of conversion therapy	.170*** (.010)	.157*** (.012)	.146*** (.013)	.151*** (.018)	.105** (.037)
Pre-treatment average outcome	.309	.330	.345	.411	.447
Observations	1,044,120	932,635	814,947	386,456	53,679
<i>Ran away</i>					
Effect of conversion therapy	.078*** (.007)	.079*** (.008)	.086*** (.010)	.108*** (.015)	.047 (.028)
Pre-treatment average outcome	.061	.053	.045	.039	.061
Observations	709,177	641,848	561,117	250,213	35,522
Cohort-individual fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Cohort-time fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Social transition controls	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Notes: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. This table assesses the robustness of the DID estimates to using only cohorts that experienced conversion therapy recently. The baseline estimate is reported in Column 1, which uses the full analysis sample. Columns 2 through 5 incrementally omit cohorts according to the number of years they experienced conversion therapy prior to taking the survey. So a cutoff of ten years implies we dropped all cohorts that first experienced conversion therapy ten or more years before taking the survey. The final cutoff is five years, the strictest threshold possible given the five-year post-treatment event window. All regressions include cohort-individual and cohort-time fixed effects as well as cohort-specific controls for socially transitioning, and are weighted by synthetic DID weights. Robust standard errors are clustered by individual and reported in parenthesis.

Table A.10: Robustness of Five-Year Difference-in-Differences Estimates to Subsample.

	(1) (baseline)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Subsample:	Full sample	Support- ive family	No rejection	Support & No reject	No con- current life events
<i>Attempted suicide</i>					
Effect of conversion therapy	.170*** (.010)	.156*** (.013)	.146*** (.019)	.096*** (.023)	.165*** (.011)
Pre-treatment average outcome	.309	.247	.250	.161	.312
Observations	1,044,120	394,820	291,506	99,545	965,109
<i>Ran away</i>					
Effect of conversion therapy	.078*** (.007)	.078*** (.009)	.028** (.010)	.043** (.013)	.076*** (.008)
Pre-treatment average outcome	.061	.046	.008	.00	.077
Observations	709,177	345,482	156,387	99,351	662,986
Cohort-individual fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Cohort-time fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Social transition controls	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Notes: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. This table reports the baseline DID estimates for exposure to conversion therapy in Column 1, and tests the robustness to using alternative subsamples, dropping both treated and control observations. Column 1 uses the full sample. Column 2 uses only respondents who report having a supportive family when asked, "You said some or all of your immediate family you grew up with (mother, father, sisters, brothers, etc.) know that you are trans. On average, how supportive are they of you being trans?" Column 3 uses only respondents who do not report any form of family rejection; we drop any observations that report any of the following: 1) Spouses/partners ended relationship because you are trans, 2) Children ever stopped speaking to you or spending time with you because you are trans, 3) Family members are either "unsupportive" or "very unsupportive" of you being trans, 4) Immediate family members they grew up with stopped speaking to you for a long time or ended your relationship, 5) Immediate family members they grew up with were violent towards you for being trans, 6) Immediate family members they grew up with kicked you out of the house for being trans, 7) Immediate family members they grew up with did not allow you to wear the clothes that matched your gender, 8) Immediate family members they grew up with sent you to a therapist, counselor, or religious adviser to stop you from being trans. Column 4 uses only respondents who report having a supportive family (as in Column 2) and do not report any forms of family rejection for being trans (as in Column 3). Column 5 drops respondents who report starting conversion therapy at the same age as another life retrospective life event, which includes the following: 1) Felt their gender was different, 2) Thought of themselves as transgender, 3) Told others transgender, 4) Full-time as gender different than the one assigned at birth, 5) Went to court for legal name change, 6) Starting puberty blocking hormones, 7) Starting hormone treatment, 8) First surgery for gender transition. All regressions include cohort-individual and cohort-time fixed effects as well as cohort-specific controls for socially transitioning, and are weighted by synthetic DID weights. Separate synthetic DID weights are estimates for each subsample. Robust standard errors are clustered by individual and reported in parenthesis.

Table A.11: Robustness of One-Year Event Study Estimates to Subsample.

	(1) (baseline)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Subsample:	Full sample	Supportive family	No rejection	Support & No reject	No concurrent life events
<i>Attempted suicide</i>					
Effect of conversion therapy	.049*** (.014)	.091*** (.025)	.044 (.037)	.060 (.063)	.028 (.016)
Pre-treatment average outcome	.356	.288	.309	.237	.357
Observations	11,434	3,835	1,806	716	9,261
<i>Ran away</i>					
Effect of conversion therapy	.028** (.009)	.034** (.012)	.016 (.015)	.015 (.019)	.036*** (.010)
Pre-treatment average outcome	.059	.042	.007	00	.076
Observations	9,064	3,638	1,341	1,308	7,249
Cohort-individual fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Cohort-age fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Cohort-year fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Social transition controls	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Notes: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. This table reports the baseline event study estimates for exposure to conversion therapy in Column 1, and tests the robustness to using alternative subsamples, dropping both treated and control observations. Column 1 uses the full sample. Column 2 uses only respondents who report having a supportive family when asked, "You said some or all of your immediate family you grew up with (mother, father, sisters, brothers, etc.) know that you are trans. On average, how supportive are they of you being trans?" Column 3 uses only respondents who do not report any form of family rejection; we drop any observations that report any of the following: 1) Spouses/partners ended relationship because you are trans, 2) Children ever stopped speaking to you or spending time with you because you are trans, 3) Family members are either "unsupportive" or "very unsupportive" of you being trans, 4) Immediate family members they grew up with stopped speaking to you for a long time or ended your relationship, 5) Immediate family members they grew up with were violent towards you for being trans, 6) Immediate family members they grew up with kicked you out of the house for being trans, 7) Immediate family members they grew up with did not allow you to wear the clothes that matched your gender, 8) Immediate family members they grew up with sent you to a therapist, counselor, or religious adviser to stop you from being trans. Column 4 uses only respondents who report having a supportive family (as in Column 2) and do not report any forms of family rejection for being trans (as in Column 3). Column 5 drops respondents who report starting conversion therapy at the same age as another life retrospective life event, which includes the following: 1) Felt their gender was different, 2) Thought of themselves as transgender, 3) Told others transgender, 4) Full-time as gender different than the one assigned at birth, 5) Went to court for legal name change, 6) Starting puberty blocking hormones, 7) Starting hormone treatment, 8) First surgery for gender transition. All regressions include cohort-individual and cohort-time fixed effects as well as cohort-specific controls for socially transitioning, and are weighted by synthetic DID weights. Separate synthetic DID weights are estimates for each subsample. Robust standard errors are clustered by individual and reported in parenthesis.

Table A.12: Correlates of the Timing of Conversion Therapy.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Felt gender was different	-0.0033 (0.0062)		-0.0031 (0.0061)	-0.0017* (0.0007)	0.0110 (0.0080)
Thought of themself as trans	0.0204** (0.0064)		0.0206** (0.0064)	0.0022*** (0.0006)	0.0021 (0.0073)
Told others they are trans	0.0926*** (0.0110)		0.0924*** (0.0110)	0.0023*** (0.0004)	0.0006 (0.0109)
Lives full-time as gender	0.1262*** (0.0211)		0.1206*** (0.0212)	0.0025*** (0.0005)	0.0007 (0.0268)
Went to court for name change	0.0874 (0.1131)		0.0341 (0.1192)	0.0007 (0.0015)	0.3106*** (0.0830)
Started hormone therapy		0.2742*** (0.0654)	0.1915** (0.0703)	0.0042* (0.0017)	0.1602 (0.1096)
Used puberty blockers		-0.0423 (0.1081)	-0.0479 (0.1003)	-0.0035 (0.0035)	0.0640 (0.1183)
Had surgery for transition		0.0308 (0.0687)	0.1025 (0.0745)	0.0008 (0.0023)	0.2211*** (0.0588)
Observations	16,831	16,831	16,831	11,434	16,717
Cohort-individual fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Cohort-age fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Cohort-year fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Synthetic unit weight				✓	
Inverse probability weights					✓

Notes: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. This table tests if socially transitioning or medically transitioning correlates with the timing of conversion therapy. This table reports regression coefficients where the outcome is a dummy variable for ever having had conversion therapy. The regressions use the stacked sample of from our event study analysis. All regressions include cohort-individual, cohort-age fixed effects, and cohort-calendar year fixed effects. Robust standard errors are clustered by individual and reported in parenthesis.

B. Online Appendix – Description of Data

This appendix explains how the retrospective panel was constructed using the 2015 United States Transgender Survey (USTS). We also describe limitations of the data, such as recall bias and heaping.

B.1. USTS Questionnaire and Topic Order

According to the Methodology report of the 2015 United States Transgender Survey (USTS), “the questionnaire contained a total of 324 possible questions in thirty-two discrete sections addressing a variety of subjects, such as experiences related to health and health care access, employment, education, housing, interactions with law enforcement, and places of public accommodation. The online survey used skip logic, which created unique pathways through the questionnaire, with each next step in a pathway being dependent on an individual respondent’s answer choices. This allowed respondents to move seamlessly through the questionnaire, receiving only questions that were appropriate for them. For example, respondents who reported that they had served in the U.S. Armed Forces, Reserves, or National Guard received a series of questions about their military service, but those who had not served did not receive those questions. Due to the customized nature of the survey using skip patterns, the length varied greatly between respondents, and no respondent received all possible questions.” The estimated completion time of the survey was approximately 60 minutes.

A list of the 32 subjects in the questionnaire is provided in Table B.1. The length of the survey may create concerns about respondent fatigue, so it is important to note that our study only used information from the first 13 subjects.

Our study used a retrospective panel (discussed in detail in the next subsection), enabling us to include person-specific fixed effects in our regression specification, controlling for all characteristics of the respondents that do not vary over the course of their life. We are therefore primarily interested in questions about how a characteristic changes over the course of the respondents’ life. There are 11 such questions, which are listed in Table B.2. All of these questions ask respondents for their age when an important life event first occurred, such as social and medical transition milestones like telling others that you are transgender or starting hormone therapy. Respondents are never given the option to report the calendar year of an event; they must report their age. We can, however, estimate the implied calendar year, since the entire survey took place in 2015 and we know the respondents’ age during the survey.

B.2. Retrospective Panel Construction

Table B.2 lists the main variables used in our analysis: 1) the respondents’ age and 2) the respondent’s age when important life events first occurred, including conversion therapy, attempting suicide, running away, feeling their gender was different, thinking of themselves as transgender, living full-time as their self-identified gender that is different from their sex assigned at birth, going to court for a legal name change, starting puberty blockers, starting hormone therapy, or having surgery for their gender transition.

We construct our retrospective panel by expanding the cross-sectional data, adding an

additional row for every age-year of the respondent. For example, if a respondent was 18 years old when they took the survey, then the respondent would have 18 observations in the respective panel, enumerated by age, from age 1 to age 18. Each of the above life events are coded as dummy variables, taking value 0 before the event occurred and value 1 during and after the event occurred. Suppose the same 18-year-old respondent reports being 16 years old when they first had conversion therapy. They also report never having attempted suicide. The cross-sectional data for this respondent would be:

Person ID	Age	Survey year	Age first had conversion therapy	Age when first attempted suicide
1	18	2015	16	Never

The corresponding retrospective panel for this respondent would be:

Person ID	Age	Implied year	Conversion therapy	Attempted suicide
1	1	1998	0	0
1	2	1999	0	0
1	3	2000	0	0
1	4	2001	0	0
1	5	2002	0	0
1	6	2003	0	0
1	7	2004	0	0
1	8	2005	0	0
1	9	2006	0	0
1	10	2007	0	0
1	11	2008	0	0
1	12	2009	0	0
1	13	2010	0	0
1	14	2011	0	0
1	15	2012	0	0
1	16	2013	1	0
1	17	2014	1	0
1	18	2015	1	0

B.3. Recall Bias and Heaping

In this subsection, we inspect the distribution of the age respondents report being when significant life events occurred, investigating recall bias; the ability of respondents to accurately report their during significant life events retrospectively. Since we do not know the true age of the respondent during these major life events, we cannot directly measure recall bias. We can, however, indirectly gauge the presence of recall bias by testing for heaping, conjecturing that major life are not more likely to occur at years or ages that are the nearest multiple of five or ten. Under this premise, we can visually inspect the distribution of the retrospective age variables to test for recall bias. If there are spikes in the distribution at multiples of

five, then recall bias is certainly a concern. If the distribution is relatively smooth around multiples of five, then recall bias is less concerning. We also conduct this test for the implied calendar year.

As past events become more distant memories, recall bias becomes a greater concern. To test for such a link between the time past since an event and recall bias, we cut the sample, comparing the distribution for recent events (less than ten years prior) to distant events (10 or more years prior).

Figure B.1 depicts the distribution of the respondents age at the survey. The USTS respondents tend to be young. Because the respondents of the survey are young, the distribution of the implied year of all life event will lean towards 2015, which is the year of the survey.

Figure B.2 depicts the distribution of the age and implied calendar year of respondents when they were first exposed to conversion therapy. Since this variable provides the information for our treatment indicator, recall bias is of greatest concern relative to the other questions. Figure B.2a shows evidence of heaping by age, there are particularly large spikes at ages 5, 10, 25, 30, 35, and 40. However, there is not evidence of heaping by calendar year (Figure B.2b). When we only consider events that occurred within ten years, the evidence of heaping is severely diminished (Figure B.2c). The heaping is driven almost entirely by respondents recalling distant life events (Figure B.2d). In short, heaping by age is an issue, but it can be mitigated by looking only at recent life events.

A similar story as above is found for all but one other retrospective variable (Figures B.3-B.12). As shown by Figure B.3, there is very little evidence of heaping in the distribution of first suicide attempts, which is our primary outcome variable. This is consistent with first suicide attempts being such a significant life event that respondents are able to recall their age at the time accurately, even if the event took place many years prior.

Table B.1: Question Topics by Section of the USTS

Question	Topic	Sub-question topics
1	Survey eligibility	(18 subquestions). Already completed survey, current state, 18 or older, transgender status, and how learned about survey.
2	Identity & Demographics	(25 subquestions). Sex assigned at birth, gender identity, pronouns, sexual orientation, racial identity, religion, age, marital status, state, disability, language, education, living situation, and cell phone.
3	Social transition-ing	(4 subquestions). Age felt gender different, age thought trans, age told others trans, socializing with other trans people, familial knowledge of trans status
4	Social transition-ing consequences	(12 subquestions). Other people's knowledge of transgender status (boss, family, school) and their reaction (supportive, violent, ended relationship), ran away from home.
5	Religious Community	(7 subquestions). Membership in a religious or spiritual community, rejection from religious community, support in religious community, knowledge of transgender status in community and their reaction.
6	Illegal work	(12 subquestions). Sex work activities, arrests, police violence, criminal justice outcomes, paid for selling drugs, hacking, media piracy.
7	Employment and Income	(14 subquestions). Household composition, employment status, union status, government transfers, income sources, total income.
8	Military	(21 subquestions). Branch of military, current status, military health care, discharge, knowledge of transgender status and the response of leadership.
9	Immigration	(9 subquestions). Immigration detention, knowledge of transgender status while in detention, separation from others, solitary confinement, physically assaulted, sexually assaulted, asylum

Table B.1: Question Topics by Section of the USTS (*continued*)

Question	Topic	Sub-question topics
10	Legal name change	(18 subquestions). Ever try/complete legal name change, judge/court's knowledge of transgender status and reactions/discrimination, age went to court for name change, legal help, legal documents changed gender and reasons why or why not.
11	Insurance	(11 subquestions). Insurance status, insurance coverage provider, insurance covers or denied gender affirming care, provider's knowledge of trans care, travel for care.
12	Health	(21 subquestions). General health, mental health, access to care, doctor's knowledge of trans care, discrimination or assault by care provider, desire for gender affirming care, access to gender affirming care, age started gender affirming care, detransitioning.
13	Conversion therapy	(6 subquestions). Ever discuss gender identity with professional, professional tried to stop you being trans, age first time professional tried to stop you from being trans, conversion therapy by religious counselor, sexual orientation conversion therapy.

Notes: We do not use any data gathered from questions 14-31, so we omit these questions from the table for brevity.

Table B.2: Age-Based Variables

Variable	Survey question
1 Age	Q2.13 What is your current age?
2 Conversion therapy	Q13.3 How old were you the first time a professional tried to make you identify only with your sex assigned at birth (in other words, try to stop you being trans)?
3 Attempted suicide	If reported one suicide attempt: Q16.10 How old were you when you tried to kill yourself? If reported multiple suicide attempts: Q16.11 How old were you the first time you tried to kill yourself?
4 Ran away	Q4.10 At what age did you run away from home because you are trans?
5 Felt gender was different	Q3.1 At about what age did you begin to feel that your gender was “different” from your assigned birth sex?
6 Thought of themselves as transgender	Q3.2 At about what age did you start to think you were trans (even if you did not know the word for it)?
7 Told others transgender	Q3.3 At about what age did you first start to tell others that you were trans (even if you did not use that word)?
8 Full-time as gender different than the one assigned at birth	Q1.13 How old were you when you started to live full-time in a gender that is different from the one assigned to you at birth?
9 Went to court for legal name change	Q10.9 How old were you when you went to court to get your legal name change?
10 Puberty blocking hormone	Q12.11 At what age did you begin taking Puberty Blocking Hormones?
11 Hormone treatment	Q12.10 At what age did you begin hormone treatment/HRT treatment?
12 Surgery for gender transition	Q12.19 You said that you had at least one procedure for your gender transition. At what age did you have your first procedure (other than hormones)?

Figure B.1: Distribution of the Respondent's Age During the Survey.

Notes: Figure B.1 is a histogram depicting the distribution of the age of each respondent when they took the survey.

Figure B.2: Distribution of the Age and Year when Began Conversion Therapy.

(a) Age when began conversion therapy

(b) Implied year when began conversion therapy

(c) Distribution if event occurred within 10 years of survey

(d) Distribution if event occurred 10 or more years before survey

Notes: Figure B.2a is a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they first were exposed to conversion therapy. Figure B.3b is a histogram depicting the distribution of the implied calendar of their first exposure to conversion therapy. Figure B.2c is also a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they first were exposed to conversion therapy, but conditions on the event occurring within ten years of the survey, assessing recall bias or recent events. Figure B.2d is also a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they first were exposed to conversion therapy, but conditions on the event occurring ten or more years before the survey, accessing recall bias of distant events. Respondents who had never had conversion therapy are omitted. The data for conversion therapy comes from the following question: How old were you the first time a professional tried to make you identify only with your sex assigned at birth (in other words, try to stop you being trans)?

Figure B.3: Distribution of the Age and Year when First Attempted Suicide.

(a) Age when first attempted suicide

(b) Implied year when first attempted suicide

(c) Distribution if event occurred within 10 years of survey

(d) Distribution if event occurred 10 or more years before survey

Notes: Figure B.3a is a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they first attempted suicide. Figure B.3b is a histogram depicting the distribution of the implied calendar year of their first suicide attempt. Figure B.3c is also a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they first attempted suicide, but conditions on the event occurring within ten years of the survey, assessing recall bias or recent events. Figure B.3d is also a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they first attempted suicide, but conditions on the event occurring ten or more years before the survey, accessing recall bias of distant events. Respondents who had never attempted suicide are omitted. The data comes from two questions. If the respondent reported a single suicide attempt in the preceding question, then they are asked, "Q16.10 How old were you when you tried to kill yourself?" If the respondent reported multiple suicide attempts in the preceding question, then they are asked, "How old were you the first time you tried to kill yourself?"

Figure B.4: Distribution of the Age and Year when First Ran Away.

(a) Age when first ran away from home

(b) Implied year when first ran away from home

(c) Distribution if event occurred within 10 years of survey

(d) Distribution if event occurred 10 or more years before survey

Notes: Figure B.4a is a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they first ran away from home. The USTS top-codes the age at 21 years old. Figure B.4b is a histogram depicting the distribution of the implied calendar year when they first ran away from home. Figure B.4c is also a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they first ran away, but conditions on the event occurring within ten years of the survey, assessing recall bias or recent events. Figure B.4d is also a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they first ran away, but conditions on the event occurring ten or more years before the survey, accessing recall bias of distant events. Respondents who had never ran away from home are omitted. The data comes from the following question: At what age did you run away from home because you are trans?

Figure B.5: Distribution of the Age and Year when First Felt Gender was Different than Assigned Birth Sex.

(a) Age when first felt gender was different than assigned birth sex

(b) Implied year when first felt gender was different than assigned birth sex

(c) Distribution if event occurred within 10 years of survey

(d) Distribution if event occurred 10 or more years before survey

Notes: Figure B.5a is a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they first felt their gender was different. Figure B.5b is a histogram depicting the distribution of the implied calendar year when they first felt their gender was different. Figure B.5c is also a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they first felt their gender was different, but conditions on the event occurring within ten years of the survey, assessing recall bias or recent events. Figure B.5d is also a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they first felt their gender was different, but conditions on the event occurring ten or more years before the survey, accessing recall bias of distant events. Since the USTS only interviewed transgender people, almost every respondent reported an age when feeling their gender was different for the first time, the variable is missing for .78% of the respondents. The data comes from the following question: At about what age did you begin to feel that your gender was “different” from your assigned birth sex?

Figure B.6: Distribution of the Age and Year when First Thought of Themselves as Transgender.

(a) Age when first thought of themselves as transgender

(b) Implied year when first thought of themselves as transgender

(c) Distribution if event occurred within 10 years of survey

(d) Distribution if event occurred 10 or more years before survey

Notes: Figure B.6a is a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they first thought of themselves as transgender. Figure B.6b is a histogram depicting the distribution of the implied calendar year when they first thought of themselves as transgender. Figure B.6c is also a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they first thought of themselves as transgender, but conditions on the event occurring within ten years of the survey, assessing recall bias or recent events. Figure B.6d is also a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they first thought of themselves as transgender, but conditions on the event occurring ten or more years before the survey, assessing recall bias of distant events. Since the USTS only interviewed transgender people, almost every respondent reported an age when they first thought of themselves as transgender, the variable is missing for .78% of the respondents. The data comes from the following question: At about what age did you start to think you were trans (even if you did not know the word for it)?

Figure B.7: Distribution of the Age and Year when First Told Others Transgender.

Notes: Figure B.7a is a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they first told others that they were transgender. Figure B.7b is a histogram depicting the distribution of the implied calendar year when they first told others that they were transgender. Figure B.7c is also a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they first felt told others that they were transgender, but conditions on the event occurring within ten years of the survey, assessing recall bias or recent events. Figure B.7d is also a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they first told others that they were transgender, but conditions on the event occurring ten or more years before the survey, assessing recall bias of distant events. Respondents who had never told others that they were transgender are omitted. The data comes from the following question: At about what age did you first start to tell others that you were trans (even if you did not use that word)?

Figure B.8: Distribution of the Age and Year when Started to Live Full-time in a Gender that is Different than the one Assigned at Birth.

(a) Age when started to live full-time in a gender that is different than the one assigned at birth

(b) Implied year when started to live full-time in a gender that is different than the one assigned at birth

(c) Distribution if event occurred within 10 years of survey

(d) Distribution if event occurred 10 or more years before survey

Notes: Figure B.8a is a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when started to live full-time in a gender that is different than the one assigned at birth. Figure B.8b is a histogram depicting the distribution of the implied calendar year when they started to live full-time in a gender that is different than the one assigned at birth. Figure B.8c is also a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they started to live full-time in a gender that is different than the one assigned at birth, but conditions on the event occurring within ten years of the survey, assessing recall bias or recent events. Figure B.8d is also a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they started to live full-time in a gender that is different than the one assigned at birth, but conditions on the event occurring ten or more years before the survey, accessing recall bias of distant events. Respondents who had never started to live full-time in a gender that is different than the one assigned at birth are omitted. The data comes from the following question: How old were you when you started to live full-time in a gender that is different from the one assigned to you at birth?

Figure B.9: Distribution of the Age and Year when First Went to Court for Legal Name Change.

(a) Age when first went to court to get legal name change (b) Implied year when first went to court to get legal name change

(c) Distribution if event occurred within 10 years of survey (d) Distribution if event occurred 10 or more years before survey

Notes: Figure B.9a is a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they first went to court to get legal name change. Figure B.9b is a histogram depicting the distribution of the implied calendar year when they first went to court to get legal name change. Figure B.9c is also a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they first went to court for a legal name change, but conditions on the event occurring within ten years of the survey, assessing recall bias or recent events. Figure B.9d is also a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they first went to court for a legal name change, but conditions on the event occurring ten or more years before the survey, accessing recall bias of distant events. Respondents who had never gone to court for a legal name change are omitted. The data comes from the following question: How old were you when you went to court to get your legal name change?

Figure B.10: Distribution of the Age and Year when Began Taking Puberty Blocking Hormones.

(a) Age when began taking puberty blocking hormones

(b) Implied year when began taking puberty blocking hormones

(c) Distribution if event occurred within 10 years of survey

(d) Distribution if event occurred 10 or more years before survey

Notes: Figure B.10a is a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they began taking puberty blocking hormones. Figure B.10b is a histogram depicting the distribution of the implied calendar year when they began taking puberty blocking hormones. Figure B.10c is also a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they started puberty blocking hormones, but conditions on the event occurring within ten years of the survey, assessing recall bias or recent events. Figure B.10d is also a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they started puberty blocking hormones, but conditions on the event occurring ten or more years before the survey, accessing recall bias of distant events. Respondents who had never took puberty blocking hormones are omitted. The data comes from the following question: At what age did you begin taking Puberty Blocking Hormones?

Figure B.11: Distribution of the Age and Year when Began Hormone Treatment.

(a) Age when began hormone treatment

(b) Implied year when began hormone treatment

(c) Distribution if event occurred within 10 years of survey

(d) Distribution if event occurred 10 or more years before survey

Notes: Figure B.11a is a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they began hormone treatment. Figure B.11b is a histogram depicting the distribution of the implied calendar year when they began hormone treatment. Figure B.11c is also a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they started hormone treatment, but conditions on the event occurring within ten years of the survey, assessing recall bias or recent events. Figure B.11d is also a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they started hormone treatment, but conditions on the event occurring ten or more years before the survey, assessing recall bias of distant events. Respondents who had never had hormone treatment are omitted. The data comes from the following question: At what age did you begin hormone treatment/HRT treatment?

Figure B.12: Distribution of the Age and Year of First Surgery for Gender Transition.

(a) Age of first surgery for gender transition

(b) Implied year of first surgery for gender transition

(c) Distribution if event occurred within 10 years of survey

(d) Distribution if event occurred 10 or more years before survey

Notes: Figure B.12a is a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they had their first surgery for gender transition. Figure B.12b is a histogram depicting the distribution of the implied calendar year when they had their first surgery for gender transition. Figure B.12c is also a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they first had surgery for their gender transition, but conditions on the event occurring within ten years of the survey, assessing recall bias or recent events. Figure B.12d is also a histogram depicting the distribution of the age each respondent reports being when they first had surgery for their gender transition, but conditions on the event occurring ten or more years before the survey, accessing recall bias of distant events. Respondents who had never had surgery for their gender transition are omitted. The data comes from the following question: You said that you had at least one procedure for your gender transition. At what age did you have your first procedure (other than hormones)?